

PERCEIVED LEADERSHIP INTEGRITY AND TALENT RETENTION IN CORPORATE EMPLOYEES: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT

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ABSTRACT

In the context of the growing Human Capital deficit and high rates of turnover of talented employees, specifically in emerging economies like the South Asian-pacific part of the world, this study tries to investigate the role of the perceived leaders' integrity in influencing talent retention, where organizational support is considered as a mediating variable. Based on Social exchange and leader-member theory and exchange theory, the integrity of the leaders is taken as a moral signal at the micro-level, which measures the level of decision of the employee to stay with a particular organization for a long term. So to say, Organizational support is a buffer to manage (reduce) capital deficit where the turnover rate is high, with the help of perceived leaders' integrity. The data was collected from 101 employees of different corporate organizations and it was analyzed using correlation, group-difference tests, and mediation via Hayes' PROCESS Macros (Model 4). The findings support the hypothesis that perceived leaders' integrity is positively associated with both perceived organizational support and talent retention, while mediation results reveal that POS (Perceived Organizational Support) fully mediates the relationship between leadership integrity and talent retention, which means leaders' integrity affects employee retention intention primarily through employees' perception of organizational care, fairness, transparency, and support. Additionally, perception of leadership integrity may vary across employee tenure within the organization, while organizational size does not exert a significant effect. Integrating leaders' integrity and support from the organization will allow the skilled workers to work with the organization in the long run, and this research extends the contribution in tackling the talent retention issue in the companies and gives direction to CHRO's to consider these factors for sustainable human capital.

Keywords: Perceived Organizational Support, Talent Retention, Human Capital, CHRO, Perceived leadership integrity, Leader-Member exchange, Social Exchange.

INTRODUCTION

"In looking for people to hire, you look for three qualities: integrity, intelligence, and energy. And if they don't have the first, the other two will kill you." — Warren Buffett, the former chairman and CEO of

conglomerate holding company Berkshire Hathaway Inc.

In the recent decade, talent attraction and talent retention have gained momentum in organizations, where companies are spending an

enormous amount of money, time, and resources to address and formulate a strategic model to manage and maintain the sustainability of human capital globally, and particularly the emerging tension identified in the Asia-Pacific region (Ali & Guha, 2018; Uzozie et. al., 2023; Mazlan & Jambulingam, 2023). According to the HRD (Human Resource Development) annual report, it was noticed in 2023 that over 80% of employers across the Asian Pacific region are confronting the human capital deficit (Tilo, 2022). There are plethora of theoretical rationales endeavoring to determine the antecedent of the matter, which encompasses the poor Human Resource Management Framework (HRMF), conventional Leadership styles, Cultural constraints, talent development (training), transgenerational gap (of understanding), and ethical code of conduct (behaviors, integrity, transparency) (Singh, 2019; Sembiring & Damayanti, 2023). Among all of the mentioned antecedents, integrity is one of the key constituents that may mar the turnover rate in organizations. Integrity is defined at different levels, i.e., individual and cultural levels, and personal and moral levels (Musschenga, 200, pp. 222-223), but this paper focuses on the influence of organizational integrity on employees. Simmon (1999) mentioned in the Journal of Organizational Change Management that behavioral integrity is the ultimate and critical ingredient for transformational leadership (a style where leaders inspire and motivate followers to achieve a shared vision and create positive, meaningful change in individuals and organizations). In simple words, the perceived pattern of an actor's words and deeds alignment from the employer, organization, or the leader constitutes organizational integrity. For instance, the employer fulfills the commitments that have been promised and ensures transparency in words and deeds while dealing with employees, which will ensure the commitment of the employee to the employer/leader (Simons, 1999, p. 19). So to say, transparency, turning words into actions, honesty from the employer/leader is organizational behavioral integrity, and the congruence of these constructs will have a significant influence on employees, which may gauge the employee attraction (through company

reputation) and employee retention (Schmidt, 2021). Kazem et. al. (2021) worked on organizational integrity and its performance on organizational performance, where the analytical results found traces of a significant relationship between organizational integrity and organizational performance. For better understanding, employees' perception of the leader (good perception or bad perception) gauges the employee's engagement with the work, which means perception of an employee about their Leaders' integrity depicts the organizational integrity holistically at macro level and this research paper venture to peel the influential or any correlational trace exist regarding the employee's perception about their Leaders' integrity at workplace and how it effect the employee retention (if it has any significant relationship).

The chances of employee incivility at workplace are higher where the trust, transparency, word-deed, commitments are not coherent as the foremost premier relationship of a leader/employer is usually established based on trust, transparency that ensure the employee commitment for longer term as per LXM theory (Leader-Member Exchange theory) which elaborates there is a reciprocal (or transactional) relationship of employer and employee where employer give respect transparency and recognition and in return employee show commitment with the company and perform at the optimal level (Ertürk & Albayrak, 2020; also see Musharraf & Jaafar, 2023).

Perceived Organizational Support theory proposed that there is a reciprocal relationship between employee and employer (which represents the organization), which means the employee devotes commitment to the organization when he/she feels or perceives that their work/their existence, or their contribution is recognized and valued in a company and vice versa (Kurtessis et. al., 2017). Baran et. al. (2012) attempted to understand the perception of organizational support in employees' perspectives, like how they perceive that their organization is supportive in nature (or supportive to some particular designations), which would contribute to employee retention. According to Eisenberger

et. al. (2020) employees develop a general perception about an organization where they work and according to the employees, Organizational support means having fairness, supporting leaders, human resource practices and work conditions constitute as a support from the organization which also infer another meaning that to have a perception of supporting organization, integrity in organization and integrity in leaders` contribute a major role.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Integrity is a moral part (of ethics), and the moral value ground can be traced within Philosophical foundations (Dunn, 2009). Nangoli et. al. (2018) findings proposed that having integrity in leadership is an intangible component (and organizational culture can be developed without any economic expenditure), which enables employee commitment to the company and creates a win-win situation for both parties. According to the literature from 2015-2025, perceived leadership integrity builds trust, an autonomous organizational culture, ensures Human capital growth, commitment, and talent retention (Simons et. al., 2015; Engelbrecht et. al., 2017; Moorman et. al., 2018; Nangoli et. al., 2018; Cai & Song, 2025). In spite of the fact that the literature demonstration is vivid regarding the influence of perceived Leaders` integrity on employee retention would be positive because of the above-mentioned evidence base empirical studies but in last 10 years there is no single study (publicly available) conducted in India-Pakistan region and this study will allow to fulfill the academic literature gap and trace if the cultural difference influence the results of the study.

Ott et. al. (2018), in the Journal of Human Resource Management International Digest, claim that retaining talent in an organization requires more than a competitive salary, but the environment (organisational culture in IO Psychology language) where employees feel psychological safety, training, and career development. You can retain the employee if they have a salary issue. Still, you can` t hold the employee if they have a problem with the environment (Mitchell et. al., 2001), and that is why talent retention is the most studied construct

and concern in Industrial Organizational Psychology. Yet, an underpinned or underdeveloped understanding fails to recognize the implications, and myriad industries lose the most important employee. Although there are confounding variables influencing talent retention, integrity is the first factor that needs to be considered in the first place if an organization wants to lead Gen Z (Casimiro, 2023).

Employer-employee relationship is like a social exchange (theory) where employees show commitment when an organization shows commitment and vice versa, which brings the discussion from the micro level, i.e., Leaders` integrity, to the macro level, i.e., organizational level (where companies amend the policies or strategy of work or workforce) (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Research of Claudia (2018) shows that perceived organizational support is the predicting construct for organizational citizenship behavior and work as a booster to enhance job performance as when organizations feel for the employee and employee started to perceive it (as perceiving is necessary to gain the outcome, employee must be able to know that company giving recognition and worth to him/her), then they also show commitment, sincerity with the company. Organizational support ensures that their leaders are supported by the organization, and they will also be supported by their leaders (indirectly from the organization), and that is why perceived organizational support is mostly studied with leadership (Ahmed & Nawaz, 2015; Astuty & Udin, 2020; Imran & Aldaas, 2020; Hoang & Le, 2025).

Rationale

Talent retention is one of the pillars while considering the organizational development or monitoring the sustainability of an organization as a capital define the organization and without it, there is no structure of a company, yet talent retention is one of the significant challenges that almost confronted by every reputable or non-reputable company around the world whilst the labor scarcity (skill-wise or overall), employee turnover in South Asian countries is detrimental and the aftermaths, owing to this, are quite dysfunctional where numerous Human Resource

(HR) are endeavor to crack down the vibrant strategies to implement and to sustain the Human capital. This research is one of the contributions to mitigate the challenge and venture to advance the knowledge in Industrial Organizational Psychology particularly in South Asian region as there are massive amount of manuscripts available under the name of talent retention which track down the different epistemological approaches among which salary of the employee or organizational environment etc. are being addressed (uniquely and culturally relevant) but this study will struggle to announce the ontological ground (cause) of the issue (which is talent retention) which means this study exertion is to find out whether perceived Leaders' integrity is the core heart of talent retention or the turnover is the product of insufficient or incongruent perceived organizational support.

So, Leaders' integrity is basically a blueprint of philosophical foundation (which should be available in every leader for the advancement in attaining OKRs), which connects with the engine, which is Human capital or talent retention, whilst organizational support is a buffer to maintain and establish the relationship between perceived leaders' integrity and talent retention. Despite robust empirical evidence establishing perceived leaders' integrity as an antecedent factor or construct for employee job commitment, talent retention, trust, and organizational culture (Simons et al., 2015; Engelbrecht et al., 2017; Moorman et al., 2018; Nangoli et al., 2018; Cai & Song, 2025), there are three gaps that remain unresolved in contemporary literature.

Existing empirical studies are Western-centric, while the South-Asian culture is considered as Collectivist or integrated with individualism and collectivism, where the power distance, leader-follower expectations may vary, or cross-cultural generalizability is not possible, as in the last decade, there has been no such systematic study conducted or publicly available. What does social exchange mean in South-Asian culture? Or does it have the same meaning as for Western people? Social Exchange Theory (Homans, 1958) and Leader-Member Exchange theory (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995) illustrate reciprocity in employer-employee and leader-follower relationships. Few

studies integrate both frameworks simultaneously to elucidate how Leader integrity (dyadic exchange), Organizational support (institutional exchange) and Talent retention (Long-term retention, outcome) operates as a unified exchange system from the micro to macro level to ensure talent retention, specifically in Gen Z, as the coming workforce is Gen Z, whose preferences are inevitably different from their forefathers (Casimiro, 2023).

Hypothesis

H1: There is likely to be a significant positive relationship among perceived leaders' integrity, talent retention and perceived organizational support.

H2: Perceived Leaders' integrity and talent retention mediated through Perceived organizational support.

METHOD

Sample

The sample for the study consisted of 101 employees from corporate settings. The sample was collected using the snowball sampling technique, where researchers engaged corporate employees from different organisations, who were asked to participate in the research. Each participant was then asked to forward the data collection measures to more corporate employees. The sample consisted of corporate employees who had been working in their respective organisations for at least 3 months. The mean age of the participants was 27 years ($M(SD)=26.93(6.65)$). The sample consisted of 57 males (56.4%) and 44 females (43.6%).

Measures

Perceived Leadership Integrity Scale (sPLIS)

The study used 3 scales to measure the relative variables. The first scale used was the short form of the "Perceived Leadership Integrity Scale" (sPLIS) by Whelan, Stoughton, Craig, & Parry (2014), which consisted of 10 items, each to be scored on 4 point scale where 1 showed the least agreeability with the item, and 4 showed high agreeability and relatability with the item. The scale tested high for reliability ($p=0.961$).

Survey of Perceived Organisational Support (SPOS)

The second scale used for this study is the “*Survey of Perceived Organisational Support*” (SPOS) (Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison, & Sowa, 1997), which consists of 10 items to be scored on a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 refers to the lowest level of agreeability with the item, and 5 shows the highest level of agreeability with the item. The scale was tested for reliability, yielding a value of $\alpha = 0.961$, showing high reliability.

Employee Intention to Stay

The third scale used for the collection of data is the “*Employee Intention to Stay*” scale by Tang, Pamela Hudson, Butcher & Maas (2002), which consists of 5 items, each item to be scored on a 5-point Likert scale; 1 represents strong disagreement, and 5 represents strong agreement with the item. The scale tested high for reliability ($\alpha = 0.923$).

Procedure

The sample was reached out via online channels, where they were sent an online form that consisted of all 3 scales and a demographics portion. The sample was asked to fill in the form at their convenience. Each subject was encouraged to forward the form link to more corporate employees and ask them to further forward it to their contacts working in corporate settings. The data was gathered via the online form and then statistically analysed as discussed below.

RESULTS

This section of the study provides the empirical support for the suggested hypothesis that is supposed to be tested using IBM-SPSS (version 25). The analysis roadmap included reliability check of the administered instrument within cultural context, descriptives of the sociodemographic variables, independent sample t-test and ANOVA to review group differences and mediation via PROCESS macro (4) by Hayes of the intended variables i.e. Perceived leadership integrity, Perceived organizational support.

Table 01

Sociodemographic properties of sample (N=101)

Variable	f	(%)	M(SD)
Age	-	-	26.93(6.65)
Gender			
Male	57	56.4	-
Female	44	43.6	-
Marital Status			
Married	26	25.7	-
Unmarried	75	74.3	-
Position Level			
Staff	39	38.6	-
Supervisor	24	23.8	-
Manager	23	22.8	-
Executive	15	14.9	-
Sector			
Public	6	5.9	-
Private	79	78.2	-
Organizational Structure			
Mini Org. (01-100)	70	69.3	-
Small Org. (101-500)	15	14.9	-
Medium Org. (501-1000)	6	5.9	-
Large Org. (1000+)	10	9.9	-

Note: M= mean, SD= standard deviation, f= frequency

Table 02
Correlation table of variables i.e. PLIS, POS, TR (N=101)

Sr. #	Variable	N	M	SD	01	02	03
01	PLIS	101	20.56	10.20	-	0.20*	0.26**
02	POS	101	36.33	11.98	-	-	0.61**
03	TR	101	16.54	6.54	-	-	-

Note: *= $p < .05$, **= $p < .01$, ***= $p < .001$, M= mean, SD= Standard Deviation, N=sample, PLIS=Perceived Leadership Integrity Scale, POS=Perceived Organizational Support, TR= Talent Retention.

A Pearson correlation analysis was performed to test the correlation of PLIS, POS and TR (Perceived leadership integrity scale, Perceived organizational support and talent retention respectively) and their means, standard deviations and intercorrelations are reported in above mentioned table.

According to the Pearson correlation, PLIS (perceived leadership integrity) has significant positive correlation with POS (Perceived organizational support) i.e. $r = .20$, $p < .05$ and TR (talent retention) i.e. $r = .26$, $p < .01$ which support the proposed hypothesis that perceived leaders' integrity has a significant influence on employees perception about organizational support that

ultimately affect employee intention to stay with the company. Furthermore, perceived organizational support is positively and strongly correlated with Talent retention which suggests that employees intend to work with the organization when he or she perceived that their organization do recognize and care about them and ensure the support of the in their favor which in turn effect employee decision to work with the organization for a long run. Overall, the analysis reveals positive correlations among the variables, with the strongest correlation observed between perceived organizational support and talent retention, as predicted.

Table 03
Results of Independent Sample t- test comparing Gender Differences in terms of Perceived Leadership Integrity, Perceived Organizational Support, and Talent Retention (N=101).

Variables	Women (n=44)		Men (n=57)		t(df)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
PLIS	16.25	8.86	23.89	9.99	4.00(99)	.13	.80
POS	33.84	11.86	38.26	11.82	1.86(99)	.84	.37
TR	15.34	6.26	17.47	6.65	1.63(99)	.05	.51

Note: M= mean, SD= Standard Deviation, N=sample, PLIS=Perceived Leadership Integrity Scale, POS=Perceived Organizational Support, TR= Talent Retention.

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to assess gender differences within the sample. There was no statistically significant difference between men and women in perceived leadership integrity ($t(99) = 0.89, p = 0.37, \text{Cohen's } d = .80$) or perceived organizational support ($t(99) = 1.02, p =$

$0.31, \text{Cohen's } d = .37$). However, a marginally significant difference was found in talent retention ($t(99) = 1.98, p = .05, \text{Cohen's } d = .51$), suggesting that gender may have a slight effect on talent retention.

Table 04

Mean Differences in Perceived leadership integrity, Perceived organizational support, Talent retention in Three Categories of employee`s working tenure within the organization (N = 101).

Variable	03-06 Months (n = 32)		07-12 Months (n = 22)		01-03 Years (n = 24)		3+ Years (n = 23)		F	η^2
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD		
PLIS	16.31	8.40	19.81	2.00	24.29	10.29	23.30	11.38	3.80*	.01
POS	36.50	10.24	33.04	12.54	37.58	12.53	38.00	13.25	.77	.51
TR	15.68	5.74	17.09	6.50	16.87	7.75	16.54	6.54	.26	.85

Note. PLIS = Perceived leadership integrity; POS= Perceived organizational support; TR= Talent retention. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

The ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference in PLIS (Perceived Leadership Integrity), $p < .05$, although the effect size was small ($\eta^2 = .01$). No significant tenure differences were found for POS (Perceived Organizational

Support) or TR (Talent Retention). These findings suggest that employees' perceptions of their leader's integrity may increase with organizational tenure.

Table 05

Mean Differences in Perceived leadership integrity, Perceived organizational support, Talent retention in Three Categories of organization`s size (N = 101).

Variable	01-100 employees (n = 70)		101-500 employees (n = 15)		50-1000 employees (n = 06)		1000+ employees (n = 10)		F	η^2
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD		
PLIS	19.58	10.02	22.06	10.00	19.00	11.81	26.10	10.48	1.36	.26
POS	37.98	11.10	28.40	12.55	35.50	12.24	37.20	14.02	2.80	.04
TR	17.41	6.00	13.33	7.38	15.33	5.68	16.00	8.80	1.75	.16

Note. PLIS = Perceived leadership integrity; POS= Perceived organizational support; TR= Talent retention. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

ANOVA results show that there is no major group difference in terms of organizational size among Perceived leadership integrity, perceived organizational support and talent retention. This indicates that size of an organization does not matter as per this data set but the null findings could be because of numerous limitations in the

data set like uneven distribution of groups, lack of contribution of broad industries, or some other extraneous variables. This could be further studied in future research to test these null findings. So as per this data set analysis, organizational size or structure has no effect on organizational support, perceived leadership integrity and talent retention

While acknowledging the contextual constraints as extraneous variables may play a substantial role

in affecting employee intention to stay in the organization.

Table 06

Regression Coefficients, Standard Error, and Model Summary Information through simple mediation by using PROCESS macro v 4.3 (Hayes, 2022) in SPSS (version 25) for the Perceived Leadership integrity, Talent Retention and Perceived Organizational Support (N=101)

Antecedent					Consequent						
Path	B	SE	p	M (POS)	β	Path	B	SE	p	Y (TR)	
										β	
PLIS (X)	.23	.11	.05*		.20	c'	.17	.05	.07	.14	
POS (M)	~	~	~		~	b	.31	.04	.001***	.60	
Constant	31.6	2.65	.001***		~	i	3.10	1.80	.01**	~	
				$R^2 = .04$					$R^2 = .40$		
					$F(1,99) = 4.02, p = .05^*$						$F(2,98) = 31.82, p = .001^{***}$

Note. PLIS= Perceived Leadership Integrity Scale, POS= Perceived Organizational Support, TR = Talent Retention. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, $p > .05$

The results of simple mediation through PROCESS Model 4 in SPSS (version 25) as values mentioned in the table 06, indicate that PLIS (perceived leaders` integrity) predicting POS (perceived organizational support) i.e. $B = .23, SE = .11, p = .07$ which in turn significantly predicting the path B to Y (from POS to TR) i.e. $B = .31, SE = .04, p < .001$ whilst the direct effect of X on Y (effect of PLIS on TR) i.e. $c', p = .07$ is not

significant which means there is full mediation among the variables.

The overall model was significant ($R^2 = .40, F(2, 98) = 31.82, p < .001$), indicating full mediation. Therefore, the findings of the current data set of this study support the hypothesis that perceived leadership integrity influences talent retention and perceived organizational support acts as a mediator among the variables.

Research Model

Note. N = 101.
 Bootstrap sample size = 5,000.
 * $p < .05$, *** $p < 0 .001$.

Summary of Findings

1. There are positive correlations among the variables, with the strongest association observed between perceived organizational support and talent retention.
2. A marginally significant gender difference was observed in talent retention.
3. A statistically significant difference in perceived leadership integrity was found based on employee tenure within the organization.
4. No significant difference was found in relation to organizational size.
5. Perceived leadership integrity influences talent retention through perceived organizational support.

DISCUSSION

With a keen focus on the role that perceived organisational support plays, this study examines the connections between perceived leadership integrity, perceived organisational support, and talent retention. All in all, there are significant results that confirm the importance of a leader with integrity and how that affects employee satisfaction and retention which supports the findings of Nangoli et. al. (2018) as discussed in the literature review. As the study's hypotheses suggested and predicted, the perception of leadership integrity had a positive correlation with perceived organizational support and retention of talent. Leaders who were perceived to have high integrity, their organisations were seen as supportive. Moreover, employees in those organisations intended to stay with their organisation for longer. The results of this study are also linked with the social exchange theory (Cropanzano, Anthony, Daniels, & Hall, 2017) which indicates ethical leadership actions being perceived as indicators of organizational concern, motivating employees to respond with loyalty and ongoing commitment.

Another measured strong and positive relationship was between perceived organizational support and talent retention. According to Ott et. al. (2018) employees tend to stay in organisations longer when they are given a positive environment and a sense of safety, not just salary. Moreover, such an environment can be curated with an organisation being supportive towards their

employees. The mediation study also showed that the relationship between the perceived integrity of the leader and talent retention are mediated by perceived organisational support. This suggests that the perception of the employees of the organisational support is how leadership integrity influences retention. An employee's perception of how valued they are in the company may be strengthened by how honourably the leader's behaviour is with his employees, which would result in an increased retention.

With the conducted demographic analyses, there were no significant differences recorded between men and women, in how they perceive organizational support or leadership integrity. However, there was a slight difference in gender when it came to talent retention which indicates a difference between men and women in how they may commit to an organisation. Moreover, variations were seen in perceived leadership integrity when measured against the tenure of the employee, which implies that the longer someone stays in an organisation, the more likely they are to trust their leader and their integrity. Whereas, perceived organizational support and talent retention proved to have no significant variation in regards to tenure, which reflects a consistent perception of these factors as time goes. Furthermore, no significant differences were observed in perceived leadership integrity, perceived organizational support, or talent retention among different organizational sizes, which implies that the processes of leadership integrity and organizational support may hold equal importance across organizations of differing sizes. However, these results should be reviewed with a larger sample as the distribution of the organisation sizes for this study was not well balanced.

LIMITATIONS/FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Future research scholars in particular domain, may work on the limitations of this study for the in-depth investigation about different facets of human capital deficit. First and foremost limitation of the research is in limited collection of data which restrain this study to be generalized based on current findings. Mixed research method

RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

is another direction for the scholars to investigate. Nevertheless, longitudinal designs also provide another insight to this field where different industries may contribute at different times and places from the same employee. Do gender differences exist or not? Still another research question that needs to be ponder on for future as limited data or uneven demographics are the limitations of this study. Is integrity part of personality or its a sole entity different from personality would be last but not least limitation of the research and future scholars may dig down these domains.

IMPLICATIONS

This study is useful for those who are having issues with human capital deficit (scarcity of skillful workers) or those who are interested in the sustainability of current employees. The point of the study was just to investigate the intangible factors (most important than monetary in today`s competitive era). While discussing sustainability and growth, moral or ethical support for Gen Z is the need for the industry to hold the talent within the organization. This study is one of the endeavors to show that turn over rates, HCD (human capital deficit) can be handled via intangible assets which are more worthwhile and scientifically proven. In simple words, organizations must incorporate integrity (the commitment which they made should be fulfilled) in their systems in a way that employees feel or perceive that their organization really cares about them and is supportive in nature. If employees perceive that their organization provides ample opportunities to support and grow without favoritism or unfairness, trust propensity in the organization increases, which ultimately leads employees to stay with the company for the long run.

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